

THE ROLE OF A MODERN MULTI-DISCIPLINARY SPORTS COMPLEX IN
THE STRUCTURE OF MAJOR CITIES

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Abstract: *The article discusses the role of sports complexes in urban planning, types of modern sports facilities and their typology. There is information about the structure, design of sports facilities, their classification.*

Keywords: *Arena, complex, grandstand, stadium, winter sports, summer sports, building, field, small area, complex.*

The sports complex is a specially built venue for multi-faceted cultural and sporting events and conferences. In the modern imagination, sports facilities are a complex of various facilities designed for training, competitions in various winter and summer sports. The main building of the complex is the stadium, which is the main sports arena with a tribune for spectators.

During the gradual formation of the sports arena of modern stadiums, their composition and size have improved significantly compared to the ancient structure. These stadiums consist of a football field (104x69 m.) with a standard size radius of 36 m. and a 400 m. running track, as well as athletics sectors.

Depending on the capacity of the stadium, the stands are located on one or both sides of the sports arena. They can be round, oval, elliptical or other closed rings.

O'lchamlariga ko'ra stadionlar quyidagi kategoriyalarga bo'linishi mumkin:

- small stadiums with stands of 1500-3000 seats.
- Medium-sized stadiums with 2000-10000 seats and an area of at least 5-6 hectares.
- Large stadiums with 10,000-50,000 seats and an area of at least 10-15 hectares.
- Olympic-style stadiums with more than 50,000 seats and an area of at least 20-25 hectares.

The approximate system of sports facilities is given in the recommended design standards for small, medium and large stadiums (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Stadiums are categorized by size.

A sports facility is a special facility built and equipped for open or closed training sessions and competitions in various sports.

The single terminology is used in the classification of sports facilities:

1. separate open sports facilities;
2. open complex sports facilities;
3. separate indoor sports facilities;
4. Indoor complex sports facilities.

Examples of outdoor sports facilities include volleyball, basketball, handball, and soccer fields (which may be indoor).

The following is the approximate balance of a stadium with a total area of 9 on a flat surface and a grandstand with 15,000 seats.

The total area of the stadium	100 %
Outdoor sports facilities, playgrounds and grounds	34 %
Large sports facilities	12 %
Service facilities	1 %
Inner corridors and distribution areas	14 %
Landscaping	39 %

When choosing a venue, the overall composition of the master plan will affect the overall complex of the stadium.

The grandstands, in most cases, are built in the general plans of sports arenas in an oval or oval shape on both sides. There will be a football field 69x104 m. a circular track 400 m. and two athletics sectors between the football field and the track. Sports arenas in large stadiums will have additional areas for athletics training along the outer boundaries of the treadmill.

The capacity of the stands will be from 2.5 to 100 thousand seats, depending on the type of stadium.

Rooms will be provided for athletes and spectators under the following grandstand or in a separate building; for athletes - with a vestibule-warmer wardrobe, changing rooms, shower and toilet rooms, massage, medical room, rooms for referees and instructors, rest room, buffets, storage rooms for sports equipment, etc .; for spectators - cash register, lobby,

toilet, buffet (restaurant), kiosk, etc .; administrative and economic rooms - management and security, equipment, etc.

The use of different constructions and materials to ensure the visibility of the stands while sitting and standing (in the cut and plan), the filling and emptying of the stands (spectator - ways to evacuate people) greatly contribute to the formation of different types of stands. 'shows the mystery. Naturally, the sheer nature of the stands has a great influence on the overall architectural and spatial composition of the stadium.

In modern stadiums, it is customary to use double stands instead of single stands.

The use of two-story devices will serve as a protective cover for the second floor, while the rows of spectators will be closer to the sports arena. Provides dual lighting and ventilation, as well as the design of a number of additional rooms under the second floor. This allows the rooms under the stands to be of normal size, which facilitates the evacuation of people in the rooms, and saves materials used to adjust the sloping ceilings of the rooms under the single-storey stands (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Location of rooms at the bottom of the stands in modern two-story stadiums.

When viewed from the arena, the two-story grandstands have a rich plastic appearance due to the dark shadows between the floors. The one-sided grandstand, located on the west side of the sports arena, can be shaped differently in the plan for optimal visibility. It is widely used in stadiums with a capacity of 18-20 thousand seats. Straight trapezoidal or curved stands are used to accommodate large numbers of spectators. Such grandstands have a capacity of 35-40 thousand and more seats.

In most cases, the stands are divided into triangular, sloping or curved (approaching the oval) side of the sports arena.

Stadiums in Dusseldorf (Germany), Vancouver (Canada), Pasandene (Rose Bowl, California) are examples.

Another round of three-way grandstands has a large number of spectators on the west side of the sports arena, which has a positive effect on the appearance of the sports arena, especially during the afternoon competitions.

Examples of such stands are stadiums in Izmailovka (Moscow), Minsk and other cities.

Modern stadiums with a capacity of 100,000 or more seats have two- or three-story indoor stands. These types of stands have different shapes in the plan: straight, convex on the sides, oval, circular, and so on.

The optimal view diagram shows the maximum comfort of spectators standing at the farthest point (190 meters) from the football field in the large stands. However, in modern Olympic stadiums, the arena can be viewed from 240 to 250 meters only with the naked eye. These dimensions can include stands of different shapes in the plan.

The circular stands, such as the Mexico Stadium, have a capacity of 40,000 to 50,000, and a large amount of space is available for additional standing viewing.

The ellipses and S-shaped ground stands are the new stands, reflecting a modern solution at the ground-based stadium designed in Hanover. The elliptical part of the stadium is located deep in the ground, and the sickle-shaped (soil) part has the appearance of a woven hill, and this part of the tribune is located to the west of the sports arena. The elliptical stand is designed for 25,000 seats, while the sickle section is designed for 50,000 spectators.

The grandstand of the stadium, located along the sports arena in Budapest, has a sloping appearance. The construction of the grandstand is made of mixed concrete and soil. This is due to the need to accommodate a large number of spectators (100,000) around the venue. The external dimensions of the tribune extend beyond the line of sight (190 m), allowing the view of an armed eye at a distance of 240 meters or more (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Overview of grandstands in large stadiums.

The design of the stands in the plan is directly related to the construction of the section, which together determine the structural structure and architectural composition of the stand.

The following schemes are characteristic for tribune shears: single-storey, ground, reinforced concrete single-storey covered and uncoated, single-storey and two-storey mixed, ground and reinforced concrete - covered and uncoated, two-storey reinforced concrete and single-storey and double-layer metal construction.

There are several types of floor stands profile:

- ground stand, with a slope or barrier wall at the back;
- tribune below ground level;

- a partially poured (soil) stand above the ground, with a slope at the back or a part of the barrier wall below ground level;

- most of the tribune is below ground level, a small part of the tribune - on the back of the shed (soil) with two slopes or barrier wall-liters;

Constructive solutions in the stands from the ground up show the rows of spectators.

In the process of improving the stadium stands, new types of them are being created - reinforced concrete and ground mix stands. This type of grandstand was first built at the Olympic Stadium in Los Angeles (USA, 1932). The lower floor of the grandstand is on the ground slope, and the upper floor is made of reinforced concrete structures with 25 rows of seats for spectators. There are service rooms under the stands. A similar two-story grandstand was used at the stadium in Naples, with the second floor of the grandstand serving as a protective cover for the first floor.

The stands were filled and the spectators evacuated through hatches, which were built into the reception areas.

The hatch system can be open in two directions or in the form of a single leaf spread. A single spread reduces the number of spectators in front of the hatches, allowing the evacuation to take place evenly. The division of spectator seats into sections should not exceed 50 rows in each section and the row depth should be 75-80 cm. Dimensions of the spectator seat: 40-42 cm in length, 30-35 cm in width, height of the seat from the aisle floor 45 cm, width of the aisle between the rows 45 cm.

The width of the hatches should not be less than 1.5 meters and not more than 2.5 meters. The number of hatches is determined by the capacity of the hatches, ie not more than 15,000 people.

The stands must be designed for a load capacity of 400 kg per m².

The tribune profile provides an unobstructed view, with the view of the inner barrier of the track and field running track being at least 15 cm from the spectator sitting in the back relative to the eye of the spectator sitting in front. This size is determined by the size C. The size of C is 13 cm. near the curved tribune of the sidewalk. can be reduced to.

Sports pavilions, outdoor sports grounds and stadium facilities, outdoor swimming pools, yacht clubs, rowing stations, sniper rifles and stands, as well as playgrounds for various sports throughout the year (volleyball, basketball, tennis, etc.).

The pavilions have different rooms and areas depending on the purpose. Therefore, the compositional methods in their planning are of a different nature.

The simple sports pavilion has a rectangular shape and has a common entrance for women and men on the front or side of the building.

In designing the pavilions, it is necessary to provide a convenient schedule for athletes using the lobby and the flow of athletes moving towards the gym.

In a small or medium-sized stadium, it is advisable to have a sports pavilion in the center to facilitate the maintenance of all outdoor sports fields and grounds.

The following room system is provided for small sports pavilions: vestibule with hot tub, storage room, skating room, buffet, sanitary rooms, sports equipment room; with a

gymnasium, utility and service rooms, in particular: a women's and men's locker room with showers and toilets, a massage room, a medical room, an instruction room, equipment, a radio station, a heating and ventilation room.

There are also large sports pavilions of various sizes, which include several gyms, swimming pools, diving facilities and more. Such pavilions will improve the quality of training in sports and provide more efficient use of the building and the stadium.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Gagin Yu.A. Sporting soorujeniya. M., 1976.
- [2] Catalog of sports inventory and equipment for the establishment of children's sports facilities. T., Uzbekistan, 2006.
- [3] Konenko I., Malaxov G. M. Sporting soorujeniya. Short directory. Profizdat. 1960.
- [4] Light athletics and the rule of sorevnevaniya, M., FiS, 1984.
- [5] Nikoleenko A.V. Sporting soorujeniya. Directory for the Faculty of Physical Education of the Pedagogical Institute. M., Prosveshchenie, 1976.
- [6] Palikarpov A. Sportivnye soorujeniya. M., FiS, 1972. Rules of the game in football. T., 2002.